

Reflection: Maybe “He” Was Born That Way

‘Queer Jesus’ love for Queers’ — I do not doubt that this is a very controversial reflection, but it is designed to make you think about how the Church has “othered” people out of the light. It is a reclamation of Jesus Christ for all Queer people, extending that notion to anyone who feels oppressed and marginalised. Nothing will get in the way of Jesus’ love for all, and sometimes it is worth “pushing against” or “putting to the test” the status quo, particularly when such a status quo has caused so much pain, death, and misery to millions of people around the world.

[‘STRENGTH FROM SCARS’ - Robert Charles Kavanagh](#)

Nov 8, 2022

[\(Artwork by Tony Rubino, “Rainbow Jesus” \(2021\), on acrylic\)](#)

(Please refer to the endnotes throughout, which will give you the extensive multidisciplinary foundation on which this essay rests. There is also a comprehensive Bibliography for further

reading. Both are after the conclusion of the essay.)

[\(Artwork by Emmanuel Garibay, “Third Day” \(2013\), oil on wood — a Christ of the people in a white tank top\)](#)

Reflection: Maybe “He” Was Born That Way [1]

Introduction:

Pope Benedict XIV (b. 1927) raised the problem of the “impression” that there is relatively scant evidence of the person of Jesus Christ and that only in the latter centuries was Christ ascribed with Divinity with a reasonable degree of certainty; and that the: “Intimate *friendship* with Jesus, *on which everything depends*, is in danger of *clutching at thin air*.”^[2] Jesus Christ is the image of God (*imago Dei*), God in the flesh, Who is the centre of the Christian faith. Christology is the study of Jesus Christ originating from the New Testament, particularly the four canonical Gospels universally recognised as reflecting Christ’s life and teachings.^[3] Christology also considers the Trinity of God the Father, Christ the Son (i.e., the second Person in the Trinity) and the Holy Spirit.^[4]

Christology aims to make sense of Jesus Christ’s teachings and deeds and His role in God’s plan for the salvation of all: “**the central defining act for his identity**.”^[5] Nevertheless, Jesus of Nazareth (vis-à-vis Christ) is also “fully human”: the carpenter’s son, who has a mother named Mary and four brothers.^[6] As we moved through the Bible and inspired Theology throughout the centuries, we were privileged to understand and familiarise ourselves with the

personal Jesus and contemplate the many *reasons* for Christ's humanity. What happened?

The challenge for the Church

However, the reality is that Christianity is haemorrhaging *en masse* and swiftly. Many academics and social scientists have found Christianity's decline in prominence and power worldwide.^[7] This leads to the question, "Why is this so?" For an *inclusionary* "mantra," why is there so much *exclusion*? Moreover, why would Christianity (in general) allow it to occur without revisiting its thinking for survival? Literally regulating ***the relationship between individuals and God*** is a critical problem.

Many people feel "*othered*" in life.^[8] It is a psychological phenomenon in the mind and soul of a "*victim*" as a direct result of a "*perpetrator*." Another term for "*other*" is "***queer***." Furthermore, "*queer*" is more commonly known as a descriptor for people who identify as LGBTIQ+.^[9]

For this essay, the principal notion of queerness broadly defines a group of people unified by their performative disregard for, dissent against, and rejection of ***compulsory heterosexuality***. It will examine Christology through the lens of the victimisation of queer people by the Church on that basis and the inextricable link to the crisis of its failure to acknowledge Jesus' queerness and the love He has for *all* queer people. Many Churches have become ***closed***

shops, and the only way to get a ticket is to maniacally self-deprecate and suppress one's naturally formed identity. It is a recipe for failure.

Those who penned the New Testament tried to make sense of something that defied their language. What the historical Life, Death, and Resurrection of Jesus Christ meant for the Church was still felt centuries after it happened (and interpreted under the guidance of the Holy Spirit). However, the Spirit's leading was not mechanical, and the words were insufficient (as words always are). As She travels throughout the marginalised and the oppressed, the Church must never stop proclaiming Christ and, as a result, must continually **improve her thinking and find new ways to explain the Bible**.

For what reasons must she restrict this procedure strictly? Should she avoid ontological distinctions in favour of a more purely practical Christology? Given the Biblical epistemology's emphasis on knowing God through revelation and God's ultimate unknowability in Godself, **are her ontological distinctions ever final?** If the Church had to depart from Biblical terminology in its pronouncements at *Nicaea (Constantinople)* and *Chalcedon* to answer the questions being asked, **what should we do with this terminology now?**[\[10\]](#)

Queer Christology — Introduction:

(Image available from [Pinterest](#))

Through a Christological *assay* “from below to above” of Jesus,^[11] this essay will demonstrate that all Christians must be able to comprehend a Queer Christology that manifests itself through Jesus’ “fully human” and “fully Divine” natures. Churches (and non-Church attending believers) need to engage with the world; thus, the Christian faith must have its social character based on this understanding, which can be achieved through the first step of intellectually contemplating critical queer and social theories to achieve what Jurgen Moltmann terms as “Jesus’ praxis:” inserting Jesus into the meaning of today’s life, inevitably leading to the oppressed, the poor, the marginalised, and the queer.^[12]

According to Reinhold Niebuhr, Jesus will always relate to culture: culture and Christianity should complement each other[13], characterising Christians' ministry and life in the postmodern era.[14] Christ's identification with the suffering and His ability to reconcile victims and perpetrators provide the key to understanding God's radical proximity in His Ministry, Death, and Resurrection. The Church should be a place where people are reminded of God's narrative through vernacular[15] and should share and reflect Jesus' love of the **whole creation**:

*To be 'queer' means to stir things up and even perhaps spoil them, in order not to settle for the easy answers of the status quo. The queer Christ articulates a solidarity with the 'fags', 'bitches' and 'n*gg*rs' of his day and our day, in order to show that the God consciousness of each person goes beyond the limitations of one's own physical existence. The incarnation of God in a human body (whether it is Jesus' alone or that of every human person) demonstrates that the Divine and the physical intersect in a powerful and mystical way, that the physical is important and can never be divorced from the spiritual, and that the Divine yearns to become one with the human over and over again, resulting in the eternal cycle of birth and rebirth, death and resurrection, creation and salvation.[16]*

Regarding Queer Theology, this essay will concentrate on contextualising Christology for people who cannot be placed within hetero-normalised gender categories due to the lack of prevalence of (or denial of) *sexuality* in the Bible.[17] This essay will not

only *queer Jesus* through some robust Queer Theology and hermeneutics but also consider Him as “fully human” within a neuroscientific, cultural, and anthropological context (complimenting the Queer Theology). The underlying thesis of this essay is that Jesus Christ was the ultimate recapitulated *imago Dei*, which means that **all** humans reflect the image of God, vis-a-vis, including humanity’s queerness (otherness), reflecting Jesus as the ultimate *imago Dei*.

Jesus’ queerness through experiencing “full humanity:” Introductory remarks:

Jesus was queer (an outsider) and possibly experienced homosexual inclinations (by scientific speculation). In surmising as such, this essay seeks to reveal the underbelly of hypocrisy inherent in quarters of the Church. Still, more importantly, it will demonstrate that Jesus was tempted in such a way to truly empathise with the **full spectrum** of queerness in the world (i.e., all of the oppressed, marginalised, and victimised — the **others**). To conclude, the essay will arrive at a Christology that has taken a leap into the mind of Jesus and prioritised His experiences, reflections, teachings, and Redemption.[\[18\]](#)

Nevertheless, this essay entirely rests on Jesus Christ’s hypostatic union. On that, it is vital to establish Jesus as the ultimate *imago Dei* because He was “fully human” as much as He is “fully Divine;” transcendent throughout the perpetuation of the salvation-historical narrative from beginning to end.[\[19\]](#) This concept is first displayed

in depicting humankind's creation and dominion as reflected in the Divine image.[20] That is later reflected in the true firstborn (i.e., Jesus Christ), “designated as both the manifestation of God and the true human” (this designation was later ratified by the *Council of Chalcedon*, according to the Doctrine of Incarnation).[21]

Through humanity's propensity towards sin (originating from the Fall of Adam[22]), Jesus died on the Cross to make us righteous.[23] However, He does not delegate His judgement to be carried out by humanity. He delegates the ***law of universal love*** (as reflected many times throughout the New Testament).[24] Moreover, thus, the recapitulated *imago Dei* is accessible to ***all*** humans to identify with Jesus' fleshly humanity and the extent of His love (as they ***directly*** reflect Him).

Background of early Christology

Christology can be traced back to the Apostles and the Apostolic Fathers when core ideas were developed. It was not until between approximately 100–300 AD that Biblical and theological experts reached a consensus on Christ's Divinity (when many patristic fathers pontificated on these relevant issues, including Irenaeus of Lyons, Clement of Alexandria, Origen of Alexandria, and Athanasius of Alexandria).[25] Schisms occurred during this time, separating the Church of the East from the Church of the Roman Empire and reflecting the contentious political climate of the time, which reflected the ***relationship between earthly authorities and spiritual authority***. It also led to heresies like Arianism, which

denied that Jesus and the Father shared the exact everlasting nature (refer to Notes 22 to 26 below for an overall historical reflection).[\[26\]](#)

Neuro-Christology:[\[27\]](#)

[\(“Jesus Christ was gay, a drag king and gender fluid, according to a university professor of theology”\)](#)

Queer Theology has come a long way in such a short time. In considering Jesus’ “full humanity” (and specifically, his sexuality), neuro-Christological concepts buttress the direction of the argument that Jesus was queer and loved queer people.

David Clough argues that the *imago Dei* is a “special revelation of the unseen God” revealed through Jesus.[\[28\]](#) Still, he does not go as

far as Christopher Carter, who argues “that human beings can image God uniquely through their humanity.”^[29] Carter utilises Scripture to highlight the view of Jesus “as the image of God perfected” and analyses Pauline ascriptions to “the ongoing transformation of Christians” and “being transformed into the same image.”^[30] — “It speaks to followers of Jesus being transformed into the reflections of the image of God through the unveiling of [one’s] face.”^[31] Clough wishes to “minimise human uniqueness to focus on atonement,”^[32] but Carter secures the Christological reflection of the image.

He does so by utilising neuroscientific research to challenge the theological debate of the myth that the mind, brain, and body can be separate; on the contrary, the mind is embodied in the brain, which is “considered the social organ of the body.”^[33] Jesus’ mind was human, and as such, Carter argues “that human beings have the unique ability to cultivate Jesus-like mindfulness with the ultimate goal of embodying Jesus-like behaviour.”^[34] That is an inherent ability in *every* human being.

Jesus was tempted in ‘every way’

[\(Artwork by Christopher Olwage, “The Wedding of Jesus and John ‘the Beloved Disciple’ at Cana” \(2016\)\)](#)

Jesus was tempted *in every way* but did not sin.[\[35\]](#) Logically, it follows that Jesus was tempted sexually.[\[36\]](#) To argue that Jesus

was *only* tempted by reference to greed, hunger, and ego, as in the desert,[37] conflicts with the book of Hebrews, which says He was tempted *in every way* — just as humanity is/was.[38] That enables Him to empathise with *all of humanity*, not just some of it.[39] It is important to understand Jesus' brain and mind at the point of temptation from a neuro-Christological perspective: Jesus was “fully human.” He had a “fully human” brain. As pointed out by Adam Zeman, the brain “[is] the most complex system so far encountered anywhere in the universe.”[40] As Oliver Davies stresses, there is a difference between neurobiological dimensionality and everyday subjectivity.

Nevertheless, these two things are both enmeshed and exist on a continuum.[41] The feeling of sexual attraction is a neurological reaction that can occur before a person is even aware of it.[42] Utilising genetic theory, it is possible to envisage *any* “fully human” person (as Jesus was) having a random hypothalamic reaction (by way of sexual attraction). Due to a lack of evidence, it is unclear whether Jesus had such a reaction to a man; however, it is entirely possible.[43]

Furthermore, Jesus' “cognitive framework comprising mental representations for understanding the world, self and others” would have depended on His close bond with Mother Mary, His “primary caregiver and the ultimate prototype for His future relationships.”[44] This aspect of attachment theory would have provided Jesus with a secure, psychologically “confident approach to sexuality.”[45]

Sexuality is empirically settled as existing in fluidity or on a spectrum, regardless of how a person “identifies.”[\[46\]](#) This would pertain particularly to one who billions of people believe to be the most “fully human” person to have existed. And in concluding the neuro-Christological angle, Jesus, in His concern, love and desire for ***all humanity***, would have experienced sexuality in respect of ***all***. The likelihood of same-sex attraction on Jesus’ sexual spectrum is underpinned by extensive peer-reviewed and empirical scholarship, bypassing the need to re-examine (within the confines of this essay) the biological reality of same-sex desire in ***all*** species.[\[47\]](#)

To deny these facts is to deny that Jesus had a human brain, and it has been established that His mind was inextricably linked to His body. The “fully human” Jesus would have experienced the full spectrum of developmental growth stages from childhood through adulthood. Without considering the specifics of Jesus’ adolescence, it is scientifically preposterous to deny a vivid mind to the Messiah, one that contemplates humanity’s fullness.

Clement of Alexandria declared that Jesus’ sexuality did not arise in the Gospels because Jesus “was not an ordinary man.”[\[48\]](#) Whilst it is, of course, proper to say that Jesus “was not an ordinary man,” to explain away the evolutionary, neuroscientific, cultural and anthropological bases of Jesus’ sexuality flies in the face of the *Council of Chalcedon*, which had reiterated the inextricable enmeshment of God and Man, but in particular that Jesus was a “true man, the same of a *reasonable soul and body*.”[\[49\]](#)

[\(Image by Monash University, Australia\)](#)

[\(Image by Monash University, Australia\)](#)

Locating the personal Jesus and His mission via Queer Theology, hermeneutics and exegesis:

(“[Compassion in the Life of Jesus](#)”)

Theologians Robert Shore-Goss and Marcella Althaus-Reid have engaged in queer theory to model their theologies that precisely fit the needs of marginalised and oppressed individuals.[\[50\]](#) Based on the modern liberation theologians, Shore-Goss grounded his Christology primarily in the praxis instead of Jesus’ nature.[\[51\]](#) However, Joel Goh argues that Jesus’s nature is central to Christology. The liberation theology impact is evident in queer Jesus’ construction.[\[52\]](#)

Jesus **rebelled** against what was **not good**. He did not conform to social conventions: crying and wailing in public,[\[53\]](#) showing fury and causing a scene in anger,[\[54\]](#) and rebelling against the hypocrisy and crudeness of faux-religiosity.[\[55\]](#) Jesus was entirely focused on the love that humanity should have for one another.[\[56\]](#) Many modern Churches do everything that Jesus detested,[\[57\]](#) especially in wanting to **look and feel** moral, upright, and righteous whilst simultaneously treating others poorly.[\[58\]](#)

Jesus' mission pivoted from the outcasts of society: "harlots, tax collectors, promiscuous women, lepers, foreigners — all the types of people who were stigmatised (i.e., the queers)."[\[59\]](#) Jesus was perplexed by the inequality of social justice, such as notions of (Jewish or Roman) racial purity and the accumulation of wealth to the detriment of others. Furthermore, when confronted by the question of divorce, He contemplated *eunuchs*. He conceded that some people were "born that way,"[\[60\]](#) seemingly accepting a category of person, naturally born of sexuality that made it unnecessary to marry: "[He] again [used] marginal figures as exemplars of kingdom values."[\[61\]](#)

Jesus was enjoyable to be around, "a glutton and a winebibber."[\[62\]](#) He loved to tell jokes, which is consistently evidenced in the New Testament, and of course, as it is well known, He could turn water into wine (amongst other miracles).[\[63\]](#) Even children loved Him as He loved them.[\[64\]](#) Theologian Rolf Schneider believes that Jesus of Nazareth's narratives proposes that the deity, as revealed by his flesh, is fundamentally exposed to

consorting with *anybody*. It thus indicates an incredible hope for *everyone*.[\[65\]](#)

All of these things culminated in His supreme wisdom and ultimate compassion[\[66\]](#) — the ability to *be* “fully human” *with* “other fully human people;” to raise the hopes and dreams of the people who were outcasts and downtrodden, and to berate those in high religious rankings which were vain and hypocritical, who made others suffer to make themselves feel righteous.[\[67\]](#) Discussions regarding a queer Jesus also necessitate the Incarnation or the embodiment of Jesus through His Mother, the Virgin Mary.[\[68\]](#) Mother Mary can serve as the queer empowerment paradigm, as asserted by Shore-Goss, as she was an unmarried virgin when she gave birth.[\[69\]](#)

Apostle John proclaims that Jesus was the “witness of the light” in the opening of the Gospel and that those who accepted Him would become children of God.^[70] Furthermore, Apostle Paul asserts Jesus as “the very image of the invisible God,^[71] who reconciled ***all humans***, regardless of nationality, class, status, gender, or sexuality;”^[72] He made peace through His death and Resurrection,^[73] which culminated in humanity’s unity with Him (“at-one-ment”).^[74] The path of blessing is to wash the feet of those who (one believes) are beneath them in some way. Jesus gave humanity an example through His washing His disciples’ feet in The Last Supper, who then instructed them (*i.e., humanity*) to do the same as He had done for them.^[75] For instance, Fulton J. Sheen remarked, “*Nothing* that was human was foreign to Him.”

Moreover, it follows that if “*nothing* human were foreign to him,” then it would be intellectually deficient (based on today’s God-given knowledge) to extrapolate any normal biological function (or otherwise) from Jesus, both making Him *less* human and furthering a bigoted and hateful narrative that is contrary to God’s law of universal love.

Jesus, reflecting a recapitulated *imago Dei*, “persuasively invites those outside biblical traditions to become a part of the world of Jesus’ story.”^[76] Jurgen Moltmann stresses that humanity is not *imago Dei* because of a separation of the soul from the body but because of its *wholeness* “in their full, sexually specific community with one another” in the “living, dynamic connection” between

them:[77] “If the table is spread by God and hosted by Jesus, it must be a table with many connections.”[78] Theologian Felker Jones neatly summarises this concept:

He is with us and for us right down to the very marrow, his and ours, in a way that is possible because he is truly God and human. Jesus saves us by making our situation his own.[79]

Understanding that Jesus is “fully human” makes it possible to combine “a socio-rhetorical approach with queer and gender criticism ... the re-readings [attempting] to penetrate through existing homophobic and erotophobic interpretations.”[80] That is consistent with the theology of Althaus-Reid,[81] who argues that conservative theology has become so desexualised through “decency hermeneutics” that her solution “is to deconstruct and then reconstruct language indecently, in order to provoke our ingrained assumptions of decency”[82] by combining “queer and gendered hermeneutics” to expose “unacknowledged assumptions of heteronormativity.”[83] That allows for acknowledging the oppression that queer people experience because of a narrow view of Jesus’ humanity.[84]

In Jesus’ time in Palestine, “true men” held positions of power over others: *queers*, women, foreigners, and those weaker than them;[85] but Myles “flips this on its head” concerning the Markan texts, and it is helpful to demonstrate the use of queer hermeneutics on a conventionally non-sexual part of the Bible.[86]

Usually referred to as the *call of the Disciples*, Myles refers to the Gospel of Mark 1: 16–20 as Jesus’ “fishing for men” — in effect, the Disciples left everything of their socio-cultural masculinity to “elope with the alluring Jesus.”[\[87\]](#)

There was an obvious homo-attraction within a short space of time. For all of the men (especially Jesus), their company was preferable to the prestige of maintaining ingrained roles of masculinity in first-century Palestine (i.e., “the queer observation that Jesus calls his male admirers to forego a definite masculine space in favour of a counter-masculine, and even suggestively homoerotic, space”[\[88\]](#)). As D. B. Martin observes, “[Jesus] seems to enjoy the company of his male Disciples a bit more than some would think *normal*.”[\[89\]](#)

([Artwork by Unknown, "Gay Jesus"](#))

The following section in the Gospel of Mark is 14: 43–52, where Judas kisses Jesus, who is in the company of a scantily clad boy who eventually ends up naked. The above hermeneutic approach is vital to home in on the verb *kataphileo* when describing Judas' kiss: It means "to kiss with every show of affection,"[\[90\]](#) which makes the possibility that the closeness between Jesus and Judas was of a (romantically charged) nature, making Judas' treachery even more heartbreaking.

[\(Artwork by Robert Scholler, “Judas-Kiss” \(2014\)\)](#)

Many arguments have been made about the boy’s status as a prostitute,[\[91\]](#) but why the boy was with Jesus is unknown. Furthermore, the Gospel of John contains (arguably) a self-reference to the “disciple whom Jesus loved,”[\[92\]](#) who rests his head on Jesus’ chest and joins Mother Mary at Jesus’ Crucifixion. The possibility and likelihood of a homosexual relationship between Jesus and John were spoken about by Bishop Gene Robinson and rebutted by David Virtue as “appalling deconstructionism” [\[93\]](#) However, theologian Shore-Goss argues

that the relationship was likely in a Greco-Roman context.[\[94\]](#) Theologian Louis Crompton also made the point that Saint Aelred of Rievaulx, in his work *De spiritali amicitia*, described the partnership as a marriage and even suggested that clerics base their friendships on Jesus and John's example.[\[95\]](#)

[\(Artwork Artwork by James Day, "My Beloved Disciple"\)](#)

Even if Jesus had no homosexual inclinations, he certainly had nothing to say against “homosexuality” during His time on earth. In Romans 1, Paul provides commentary on homo-genitality being an instance of Gentile uncleanness (from the Jewish context), however in Romans 14: 14, he insists in his letter that “I know and am persuaded in the Lord Jesus that nothing is unclean in itself.”[\[96\]](#) Paul confirms elsewhere that “[t]he only thing that counts is faith expressing itself through love.”[\[97\]](#) Furthermore, Corinthians 6: 9 and Timothy 1: 10 reflect Jesus’ teachings for love of one another and a distaste for abusive sexual acts.[\[98\]](#)

The point is that nowhere in the New Testament does Jesus condemn one’s sexuality *based on such sexuality*. Condemnation of domestic affairs in terms of historical, anthropological, theological, and Christological hermeneutics will bring forth God’s truth about all things.[\[99\]](#) After all, preachers condemning homosexuality do not advocate for slavery even though it is supported in long passages.[\[100\]](#) They allow divorce even though it goes against Jesus’ teachings.[\[101\]](#) They do not focus on the ancient contention that the earth was flat.[\[102\]](#) For Churches that have turned their backs on authenticity and legitimacy, there will always be queer people in the community who mistakenly believe that they are not loved by God, which is tragic.

Concluding remarks:

The above Queer Christology (integrating a fresh neuro-Christological approach) has aimed to explore Jesus’ “full humanity” to connect with queer people.^[103] Jesus has two natures, though: human *and* Divine (or, alternatively, God-consciousness^[104]), which can cause some confusion.^[105] Nevertheless, it is contended that the hypostatic union of Jesus does not dissuade this essay’s arguments, and that is because Jesus did not deprecate or see anything unworthy in humanity’s condition.^[106] It dovetails with Jesus’ salvific role, allowing *all* humanity to cultivate such God-consciousness.^[107] One may assume, through His abolishment of laws in the Old Testament to create a new covenant,^[108] that He was effectively extending God’s love to *all humanity*, which the Church must reflect.

In transforming the new law, humanity is introduced to the touchstone of love: “A new commandment I give to you, that you love one another, as I have loved you.”^[109] That is the law of Jesus Christ.^[110] Paul summarises the law: “Love your neighbour as yourself.”^[111] Queer Christology reflects Jesus’ love for *all*, especially His queer people: the *othered*. In returning the Church to Christ’s mission, she must accept queer hermeneutics and exegesis to welcome back her queer children as *imago Dei* because **Queer Jesus Christ** is the Messiah of *all queer people*; a great source of Pride for the Church as she traverses the conclusion of the postmodern era.

Notes:

[1] Matthew 19: 11–12; and see reflective lyrics in Lady Gaga, *Born This Way* (Santa Monica, CA: Streamline/Interscope/KonLive, 2011).

[2] Pope Benedict XIV, *Jesus of Nazareth: From the Baptism in the Jordan to the Transfiguration* (New York: Doubleday, 2007), xii. (Note: author's emphasis).

[3] Beth Felker Jones, *Practicing Christian Doctrine: An Introduction to Thinking and Living Theologically* (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Academic, 2014), 117.

[4] *Ibid.*, 117.

[5] Richard Hays, "The Story of God's Son: The Identity of Jesus in the Letters of Paul," in *Seeking the Identity of Jesus: A Pilgrimage*, ed. Beverly Roberts Gaventa and Richards B. Hays (Grand Rapids: Eerdsman, 2008), 189.

[6] Matthew 13: 55.

[7] Jeff Haynes, *Religion in Global Politics* (London: Routledge, 2014), 80.

[8] O. Sing, K. E. G. Williams, S. L. Neuberg, "Evolutionary approaches to stereotyping and prejudice," in C. G. Sibley, F.K. Barlow, eds. *The Cambridge Handbook of the Psychology of*

Prejudice (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press; 2017), 21–46; and K. Abbink, D. Harris, “In-group favouritism and out-group discrimination in naturally occurring groups,” in *PLOS One*, 14, no. 9 (2019).

[9] “LGBTIQA+” = Lesbian, Bisexual, Transgender, Gay, Intersex, Queer, Asexual. The full spectrum can be found at <https://kidshelpline.com.au/teens/issues/lgbtiq-ultimate-dictionary>, accessed October 15, 2022.

[10] (Note: author’s personal reflection).

[11] Veli-Matti Karkkainen, *Christology: A Global Introduction* (Grand Rapids MI: Baker Publishing, 2016), 5–6; See also, generally: Gerald O’Collins, S.J., *Christology: A Biblical, Historical, and Systematic Study of Jesus*, 2nd ed. (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009); and Wolfhart Pannenberg, *Systematic Theology*, trans. Geoffrey W. Bromiley (Grand Rapids MI: Eerdmans, 1994), 2: 279.

[12] Jurgen Moltmann, *The Way of Jesus Christ: Christology in Messianic Dimensions*, trans. Margaret Kohl (Minneapolis: Fortress, 1993), 41.

(Note: From “below to above” indicates the intention to inquire into the historical evidence of Jesus, however, in a way which reveals “the above” Divine nature of Christ which will be reached in the

Concluding Remarks: generally, see, Millard J. Erickson, *Christian Theology*, 3rd ed. (Grand Rapids, Baker Academic, 2013).)

[13] Vassilios Paipais, “Reinhold Niebuhr and the Christian realist pendulum,” *Journal of International Political Theory* 17, no. 2 (2021): 185.

[14] The fact remains that the division of history into profanes and sacred does not exist: Robert E. Shore-Goss, “Queering Jesus: LGBTQI Dangerous Remembering and Imaginative Resistance,” *Journal for Interdisciplinary Biblical Studies* (2021): 62.

[15] Łukasz Wiśniewski, “Religious tourism in Christian sanctuaries: the implications of mixed interests for the communication of the faith,” *Church, Communication and Culture* 3, no. 3 (2018): 199.

[16] Thomas Bohache, *Christology from the Margins* (London: SCM Press, 2008), 213. (Note: author’s emphasis).

[17] Jonathan T. Pryor, Ángel de Jesús González, and Candace Lamb, “Exploring 20 Years of LGBTQ+ Practitioner Scholarship: Applying Scholarship to Practice?” in *Journal of Student Affairs Research and Practice* (2022): 1; see also Jessica A Boon, “At the Limits of (Trans) Gender: Jesus, Mary, and the Angels in the Visionary Sermons of Juana de la Cruz (1481–1534).” *Journal of Medieval and Early Modern Studies* 48, no. 2 (2018): 281.

[18] Hebrews 4: 14–16; and Hebrews 2: 14–18.

[19] Stanley J. Grenz, “Jesus as the imago Dei: Image-of-God Christology and the Non-Linear Linearity of Theology,” *Journal of the Evangelical Theological Society*, 47, no.4 (December, 2004): 620.

[20] Genesis 1: 26–28.

[21] 2 Corinthians 4: 4–6; and Colossians 1:15–20. See also Christopher Carter, “The Imago Dei As The Mind Of Jesus,” *Zygon*, 49, no. 3 (September, 2014): 753.

(Note: Both the *Nicene* and *Constantinople Councils* (325 and 381 AD, respectively) reaffirmed Jesus’ deity and humanity. The phrase affirmed that the Son was *homoousios* (of the same being) as the Father, and that the Father, Son, and Holy Spirit are all aspects of the same God. Jesus is both human and divine, according to the *Council of Ephesus* (431 AD). The second *Ephesian Council*, held in 451 AD, however, endorsed the Alexandrian school’s view of a single nature for Jesus Christ: the Incarnate Word of God: Veli-Matti Karkkainen, *Christology*, 41–69.

The Council of Chalcedon (451 AD) was the definitive meeting where it was agreed that Jesus was fully divine and fully human (upholding the concept of *dyophysitism*). Christians who hold to the *dyophysite* position hold that the two natures of Christ are perfectly united in one hypostasis and one person. The

Chalcedonians based their understanding of Jesus' unity on his hypostatic union (his divinity and humanity being described as nature). Those who disagreed with the Chalcedonian concept looked to his nature as the source of harmony: *Ibid.*, 41–69.)

Debates resurfaced mainly in light of the Enlightenment and Protestant Reformation of the Church, where Christ's dual nature was ratified in his deification through Incarnation against the backdrop of a preceding fully human ministry: *Ibid.*, 41–69).

[22] Genesis 3; see also Millard J. Erickson, *Christian Theology* (3rd ed.) (Grand Rapids: Baker Academic, 2015), 391.

[23] Romans 5:18–19.

[24] John 13: 34; John 15: 12; John 15: 17; Galatians 6: 2; 1 Corinthians 9: 21; Matthew 7: 12; and Galatians 5: 14; Romans 13: 10.

[25] Karkkainen, *Christology*, 41–69.

[26] *Ibid.*, 41–69.

[27] Mainly utilising the author's original ideas surrounding the neuroscientific implications of honest and complete Christology.

[28] David Clough, *On Animals: Volume 1, Systematic Theology* (New York: T&T Clark International, 2012), 101.

[29] Carter, *The Imago Dei*, 755.

[30] *Ibid.*, 755; and Philippians 2: 1–11.

[31] Carter, *The Imago Dei*, 755; 1 Corinthians 3: 1–2; and 2 Corinthians 3: 18.

[32] Clough, *On The Animals*, 101.

[33] Daniel Siegal, *The Mindful Brain* (New York: W.W. Norton, 2007), 48.

[34] Carter, *The Imago Dei*, 757.

[35] Hebrews 4:15.

[36] Joel Goh, *Jesus Was Gay*, 9.

[37] Matthew 4: 1–11; Luke 4: 1–13; and Mark 1: 12–13.

[38] Goh, *Jesus Was Gay*, 11.

[39] Hebrews 2: 14–18; and Hebrews 4: 14–16.

[40] Oliver Davies, “Neuroscience, Self, and Jesus Christ,” *Questioning the Human: Toward a Theological Anthropology for the Twenty-First Century*, eds. Yves De Maeseneer, Ellen Van Stichel, and Lieven Bouve (Fordham

University Press, 2014): Chapter 5 inclusive; see also Adam Zemani and Jan Coebberg, “The Nature of Consciousness,” in *Clinical Neurology, Vol. 118 (3rd series) Ethical and Legal Issues in Neurology*, eds. J.L. Bernat and R. Beresford (Exeter: Department of Neurology, Peninsula Medical School, 2013): 373–407.

[41] *Ibid.*

[42] *Ibid.*; see also Katherine Wu, “Love, Actually: The science behind lust, attraction, and companionship,” Harvard University: The Graduate School of Arts and Science, February 14, 2017, accessed August 8, 2022: <https://sitn.hms.harvard.edu/flash/2017/love-actually-science-behind-lust-attraction-companionship/>

[43] Davies, *Neuroscience and Jesus Christ*, 85; and Katherine Wu, *The Science Behind Lust*, website cited.

[44] See generally J. Bowlby, *Attachment and Loss* (New York: Basic Books, 1969); and Inge Bretherton, “The Origins of Attachment Theory: John Bowlby and Mary Ainsworth,” *Developmental Psychology* 28 (1992): 759–775; David J. Wallin, *Attachment in Psychotherapy* (New York: Guilford Press, 2007), 11–24.

[45] Peter C. Costello, *Attachment-Based Psychotherapy* (Washington: American Psychological Association, 2013), 21, 65–66; See also “How your attachment style shows up in sex and intimacy,” accessed August 10, 2022, <https://www.orri->

uk.com/how-your-attachment-style-shows-up-in-sex-and-intimacy/; and generally, David J. Wallin, *Attachment in Psychotherapy* (New York: The Guilford Press, 2007); and Bretherton, *Origins of Attachment*, 759.

[46] *Ibid.*, covered in footnote above and below.

[47] P. R. Adriaens, A. De Block, “The evolution of social construction: the case of male homosexuality,” *Perspectives In Biological and Medicine*, 49, no. 4 (2006): 570–585; J. M. Bailey, R. C. Pillard, R.C., “A genetic study of male sexual orientation,” *Archives of General Psychiatry*, 48 (1991): 1089–1094; A. P. Bell, M. S. Weinberg, S. K. Hammersmith, *Sexual preference: Its development in men and women* (Bloomington: Indiana University, 1981); W. Byne, B. Parsons, “Human sexual orientation. The biological theories reappraised,” *Archives Of General Psychiatry*, 50, no. 3 (1993) 228–239; K. J. Dover, *Greek homosexuality* (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1989); B. Fahs, “Compulsory bisexuality? The challenges of modern sexual fluidity,” *Journal of Bisexuality*, 9 (2009): 431–449; M. Foucault, *The History of Sexuality* (New York: Vintage Books. Ford, 1989); F. A. Beach, *Patterns of Sexual Behavior* (New York: Harper, 1951); S. Freud, *Three essays on the theory of sexuality*, trans. James Strachey (New York: Basic Books, 1951/orig. 1905); K. L. Isgro, “Troubling the Canon: Bisexuality and Queer Theory,” *Journal Of Homosexuality*, 52, no. 1–2 (2006): 159–184; A. C. Kinsey, W. B. Pomeroy, C. E. Martin, *Sexual Behavior in the Human Male* (Philadelphia: W.B. Saunders, 1948); F. Klein, B. Sepekoff, T.

J. Wolf, "Sexual orientation: A multi-variable dynamic process," *Journal of Homosexuality*, 11 (1985): 35–49; J. Money, *Gay, Straight, and In-Between: The Sexology of Erotic Orientation* (New York: Oxford University Press, 1988); F. Muscarella, "The Evolution of Homoerotic Behavior in Humans," *Journal of Homosexuality*, 40, no.1 (2000): 51–77; W. Pedersen, H. W. Kristiansen, "Homosexual Experience, Desire and Identity Among Young Adults," *Journal of Homosexuality*, 54, no.1–2 (2008): 68–102; A. Poiani, *Animal Homosexuality: A Biosocial Approach* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 210); Q. Rahman, "The Neurodevelopment of Sexual Orientation," *Neuroscience and Biobehavioral Reviews* 29, no. 7 (2005): 1057–1066; R. J. Stoller, G. H. Herdt, "Theories of Origins of Male Homosexuality," *Archives of General Psychiatry* 42 (1985): 399–404; M. D. Storms, "Theories of Sexual Orientation," *Journal of Personality & Social Psychology*, 38, no. 5 (1987): 783–792; and J. D. Weinrich, "Is Homosexuality Biologically Natural?" in *Homosexuality: Social, Psychological, and Biological Issues*, eds. W. Paul and J.D. Weinrich (Eds.) (Beverly Hills: Sage Publications, 1987): 197–208.

[48] Clement of Alexandria, *Stromata 3.49*, in *Alexandrian Christianity*, vol. 2, trans. J. Oulton and H. Chadwick (Philadelphia: Westminster Press, 1954), 40–92.

[49] Carter, "The Imago Dei," 753. See also George Johnston, "Review of Book: The Emergence of the Catholic Tradition (100–600): Volume 1 of The Christian Tradition: A History of the

Development of Doctrine,” *Religion/Sciences Religieuses*, 2, no. 3 (1976): 263–264.

[50] Robert E. Shore-Goss, Joseph N. Goh, *Unlocking Orthodoxies for Inclusive Theologies* (London: Routledge, 2020), 154.

[51] *Ibid.*

[52] Joel Goh, *Jesus was Gay*, 167–195.

[53] Matthew 4: 16; John 11: 33; and Matthew 11: 36.

[54] John 2: 13–17.

[55] Matthew 7: 15; Matthew 23; and Luke 11 and 12.

[56] John 13: 34.

[57] Ezekiel 34: 1–9.

[58] Goh, *Jesus was Gay*, 176.

[59] *Ibid.*, 176; Matthew 11: 19; and Luke 7: 34.

[60] Matthew 19: 11–12.

[61] John J. Collins, Gina Hens-Piazza, Barbara Reid OP and Donald Senior CP, *The Jerome Biblical Commentary for the Twenty-First*

Century, Third Fully Revised Edition (London: T&T Clark, 2020), 1211. Moreover, this excerpt is reflected in modern vernacular through pop sensation Lady Gaga, a Roman Catholic entertainer, through her lyrics “*I’m beautiful in my way ’cause God makes no mistakes, I’m on the right track, baby, I was born this way. Don’t hide yourself in regret, just love yourself, and you’re set, I’m on the right track, baby, I was born this way.*” Accessed on 15 October 2022, <https://www.lyrics.com/lyric/23051878/Lady+Gaga/Born+This+Way>

[62] Matthew 11: 19; and Luke 7: 34.

[63] John 2: 4; Mark 1: 16–17; Luke 6: 39; Matthew 7: 6; Luke 6: 42; Matthew 7: 4; John 11: 11–14; and Luke 11: 37–52.

[64] Matthew 19: 13–15; Mark 10: 13–16; and Luke 18: 15–17.

[65] Selina Palm, “Religion and Democracy Studies in Public Theology,” (Torsten Meireis and Rolf Schneider eds.) *International Journal of Public Theology* 13, no. 1 (2019): 109.

[66] Goh, *Jesus was Gay*, 195.

[67] Mark 2: 23–3: 6.

[68] Robert E. Shore-Goss, *Queering Jesus*, 64.

[69] *Ibid.*; and Luke 1: 26–38.

[70] John 1:12.

[71] Colossians 1:15, 19–20; and Galatians 3: 26–28.

[72] See Elizabeth McLaughlin, “Engendering the Imago Dei: How Jesus Grounds Our Lives as Parables of the Divine Image,” in *Priscilla Papers: The Academic Journal of CBE International*, April 30, 2009, accessed August 12, 2022, <https://www.cbeinternational.org/resource/article/priscilla-papers-academic-journal/engendering-imago-dei-how-Jesus-grounds-our>

[73] Colossians 1: 19–20.

[74] Galatians 3: 26–28.

[75] John 13: 13–17.

[76] McLaughlin, “Engendering,” website cited. Footnote continues on next page.

(Note: Respected Evangelical Millard Erickson hardly explicates the idea of Jesus as imago Dei and relegates Jesus the Messiah to no more than providing us with “a helpful guide” as to “what human nature is intended to be.” (Millard J. Erickson, *Christian Theology* (2nd ed) (Grand Rapids MI: Baker, 2001), 532–533); see also Stanley J. Grenz, “Jesus as the imago Dei: Image-of-God Christology and the Non-Linear Linearity of Theology,” *Journal of*

the Evangelical Theological Society, 47, no.4 (December, 2004), 624–625. Furthermore, as with Erickson above, theologian Wayne Grudem defines the concept by reference to humanity before the Fall, asserting that “it is important that we understand the full meaning of the image of God not simply from observation of human beings as they currently exist, but from the biblical indications of the nature of Adam and Eve when God created them and when all that God had made was ‘very good’.” (Wayne Grudem, *Systematic Theology: An Introduction to Biblical Doctrine* (Grand Rapids MI: Zondervan, 1994), 444; Genesis 1: 31).

[77] Veli-Matti Karkkainen, *Christology: A Global Introduction* (2nd ed.) (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Publishing, 2016), 178; Jurgen Moltmann, *The Spirit of Life: A Universal Affirmation*, trans. Margaret Kohl (Minneapolis: Fortress, 1992), 92.

[78] Letty M. Russell, *Church in the Round: Feminist Interpretation of the Church* (Louisville: Westminster John Knox, 1993), 18.

[79] Beth Felker Jones, *Practicing Christian Doctrine* (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Academic, 2014), 121.

[80] Robert J. Myles, “Dandy Discipleship: A Queering of Mark’s Male Disciples,” *Journal of Men, Masculinities and Spirituality*, 4, no. 2 (June 2010).

[81] M. Althaus-Reid, *Indecent Theology: Theological Perversions in Sex, Gender and Politics* (New York: Routledge, 2001); *Ibid.*, *The*

Queer God (New York: Routledge, 2003); *Ibid.*, “Mark,” in *The Queer Bible Commentary*, eds. D. Guest, R. E. Goss, M. West and T. Bohache (London: SCM Press, 2006), 517–525.

[82] See Myles, *Dandy Discipleship*, 68.

[83] *Ibid.*, 68; see also A. Jargose. *Queer Theory: An Introduction* (Dunedin: Otago University Press, 1997), 3.

[84] *Ibid.*, 70.

[85] C. Conway, *Behold the Man: Jesus and Greco-Roman Masculinity* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2008), 36.

[86] Further passages not examined in the interests of word limitation.

[87] Myles, *Dandy Discipleship*, 71.

[88] *Ibid.*, 71.

[89] D. B. Martin, *Sex and the Single Saviour: Gender and Sexuality in Biblical Interpretation* (Louisville KY: Westminster John Knox, 2006), 96.

[90] B. Witherington, *The Gospel of Mark: A Socio-Rhetorical Commentary* (Grand Rapids MI: W. B. Eerdmans, 2001), 381.

[91] T. W. Jennings, *The Man Jesus Loved: Homoerotic Narratives from the New Testament* (Cleveland, OH: Pilgrim Press, 2003), 109–110.

[92] John 13: 23; John 19: 26; and John 21: 7–20; see also T. W. Jennings, *Ibid*: “A close reading of the texts in which the beloved disciple appears supports the hypothesis that the relationship between him and Jesus may be understood as that of lovers. As it happens, both Jesus and the beloved are male, meaning that their relationship may be said to be, in modern terms, a ‘homosexual’ relationship,” 34.

[93] Elizabeth Day, “Jesus might have been homosexual, says the first openly gay bishop,” *The Telegraph, UK* (April 3, 2005), accessed August 8, 2022, <https://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/uknews/1487002/Jesus-might-have-been-homosexual-says-the-first-openly-gay-bishop.html>

[94] Hank Hyena, “Was Jesus Gay: A search for the messiah’s true sexuality leads to a snare of lusty theories,” accessed August 12, 2022, https://web.archive.org/web/20110217080422/http://www.salon.com/feature/1998/04/cov_10feature.html; See also, <https://www.city-data.com/forum/religion-spirituality/1030630-new-covenant-homosexuality-65.html>

[95] Louis Crompton, *Homosexuality and Civilization* (Harvard: Belknap Press, 2003), 180.

[96] See also Romans 1: 16; Romans 1: 7 and Romans 12: 4–5. Paul’s prayer is that Christians “live in harmony with one another, according to Jesus Christ.” (Romans 15: 5).

[97] Galatians 5: 6.

[98] See Daniel A. Helminiak, *What the Bible Really Says About Homosexuality* (New Mexico, Alamo Square Press, 2018), Chapters Five to Seven (inclusive); see also Matthew Vines, *God and the Gay Christian* (New York: Convergent Books, 2015), Chapter Six.

[99] Helminiak, *What the Bible Really Says*, 11–42.

[100] Ephesians 6: 5–9; Colossians 3: 22–4: 1; Timothy 6: 1–2; and 1 Peter 2: 18.

[101] Matthew 5: 32; Mark 10: 1–12; and Luke 16: 18.

[102] Genesis 1: 1–17.

[103] Shore-Goss, *Queering Jesus*, 65.

[104] Friedrich Schleiermacher, *The Christian Faith* (2nd ed), eds. H. R. Mackintosh and J. S. Stewart (London, T&T Clark, 1999), 385.

[105] “The Council of Chalcedon’s ‘Definition of Faith’,” in *The Christological Controversy*, trans. ed. Richard A. Norris Jr. (Philadelphia: Fortress, 1980), 159; see also Sarah Coakley, “What

does Chalcedon Solve and What Does it Not? Some Reflections on the Status and Meaning of the Chalcedonian ‘Definition’,” in *The Incarnation: An Interdisciplinary Symposium on the Incarnation of the Son of God*, eds. Stephen T. Davis, Daniel Kendall SJ, and Gerald O’Collins, SJ (New York: Oxford University Press, 2004), 155.

[106] Cyril of Alexandria, *On the Unity of Christ*, trans. John McGuckin (Crestwood, NY: St. Vladimir’s Seminary Press, 2000), 220.

[107] Veli-Matti Karkkainen, *Christology*, 81.

[108] Pursuant to Ephesians 2: 14–16; Hebrews 8: 13; 2 Corinthians 3: 7–11; Galatians 3: 15–29; and Acts 15: 19–20.

[109] John 13: 34; John 15: 12; and John 15: 17.

[110] Galatians 6: 2; 1 Corinthians 9: 21; and Matthew 7: 12.

[111] Galatians 5: 14; and Romans 13: 10.

Bibliography:

“How your attachment style shows up in sex and intimacy.”
 Accessed August 10, 2022. <https://www.orri-uk.com/how-your-attachment-style-shows-up-in-sex-and-intimacy/>

“The Council of Chalcedon’s ‘Definition of Faith’.” In *The Christological Controversy*. Translated and edited by Richard A. Norris Jr. Philadelphia: Fortress, 1980.

Abbink, K. and Harris, D. “In-group Favouritism and Out-group Discrimination in Naturally Occurring Groups.” *PLOS One* 14, no. 9 (2019).

Adriaens, P. R. and A. De Block. “The evolution of social construction: the case of male homosexuality.” *Perspectives In Biological and Medicine* 49, no. 4 (2006): 570–585.

Alexandria, Cyril of. *On the Unity of Christ*. Translated by John McGuckin. Crestwood, NY: St. Vladimir’s Seminary Press, 2000.

Althaus-Reid, M. “Mark.” In *The Queer Bible Commentary*. Edited by D. Guest, R. E. Goss, M. West and T. Bohache. London: SCM Press, 2006: 517–525.

Althaus-Reid, M. *Indecent Theology: Theological Perversions in Sex, Gender and Politics*. New York: Routledge, 2001.

Althaus-Reid, M. *The Queer God*. New York: Routledge, 2003.

Bailey, J. M. and R. C. Pillard. “A genetic study of male sexual orientation,” *Archives of General Psychiatry* 48 (1991): 1089–1094.

Beach, F. A. *Patterns of Sexual Behavior*. New York: Harper, 1951.

Bell, A. P. and M. S. Weinberg, S. K. Hammersmith. *Sexual preference: Its development in men and women*. Bloomington: Indiana University, 1981.

Benedict XIV (Pope). *Jesus of Nazareth: From the Baptism in the Jordan to the Transfiguration*. New York: Doubleday, 2007.

Bohache, Thomas. *Christology from the Margins*. London: SCM Press, 2008.

Boon, Jessica A. "At the Limits of (Trans) Gender: Jesus, Mary, and the Angels in the Visionary Sermons of Juana de la Cruz (1481–1534)." *Journal of Medieval and Early Modern Studies* 48, no. 2 (2018): 281.

Boswell, John. *Christianity, Social Tolerance, and Homosexuality: Gay People in Western Europe from the Beginning of the Christian Era to the Fourteenth Century*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1980).

Bowlby, J. *Attachment and Loss*. New York: Basic Books, 1969.

Bretherton, Inge. "The Origins of Attachment Theory: John Bowlby and Mary Ainsworth." *Developmental Psychology* 28 (1992): 759–775.

Byne, W. and B. Parsons, “Human sexual orientation. The biological theories reappraised.” *Archives Of General Psychiatry* 50, no. 3 (1993) 228–239.

Canales, Arthur David. “Queer Theology and Youth and Young Adult Ministry.” *Journal of Youth and Theology* 21, no. 1 (2021): 3.

Carter, Christopher. “The Imago Dei As The Mind Of Jesus.” *Zygon* 49, no. 3 (September, 2014): 753.

Clement of Alexandria. *Stromata 3.49*, in *Alexandrian Christianity*, vol. 2. Translated by J. Oulton and H. Chadwick. Philadelphia: Westminster Press, 1954.

Coakley, Sarah. “What does Chalcedon Solve and What Does it Not? Some Reflections on the Status and Meaning of the Chalcedonian ‘Definition’.” In *The Incarnation: An Interdisciplinary Symposium on the Incarnation of the Son of God*. Edited by Stephen T. Davis, Daniel Kendall SJ, and Gerald O’Collins, SJ. New York: Oxford University Press, 2004.

Collins, John J., Hens-Piazza, Gina, Reid OP, Barbara, and Senior CP, Donald (Editors). *The Jerome Biblical Commentary for the Twenty-First Century, Third Fully Revised Edition*. London: T&T Clark, 2020.

Conway, C. *Behold the Man: Jesus and Greco-Roman Masculinity*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2008.

Crompton, Louis. *Homosexuality and Civilisation*. Harvard: Belknap Press, 2003.

Davies, Oliver. “Neuroscience, Self, and Jesus Christ,” *Questioning the Human: Toward a Theological Anthropology for the Twenty-First Century*. Edited by Yves De Maeseneer, Ellen Van Stichel, and Lieven Bouve. Fordham University Press, 2014.

Day, Elizabeth. “Jesus might have been homosexual, says the first openly gay bishop.” *The Telegraph, UK (April 3, 2005)*. Accessed August 8, 2022. <https://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/uknews/1487002/Jesus-might-have-been-homosexual-says-the-first-openly-gay-bishop.html>

Day, James. *Beloved Disciple*. Artwork accessed August 13, 2022. <https://qspirit.net/john-evangelist-beloved-disciple/>

Dias, Elizabeth, “The Imago Dei Campaign: Evangelical Groups Say Gays Made in God’s Image.” *Time (January 20, 2014)*. Accessed August 9, 2022. <https://swampland.time.com/2014/01/20/the-imago-dei-campaign-evangelical-groups-say-gays-made-in-gods-image/>

Dover, K. J. *Greek homosexuality*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1989.

Erickson, Millard J. *Christian Theology* (2nd ed). Grand Rapids MI: Baker, 2001.

Erickson, Millard J. *Christian Theology* (3rd ed.). Grand Rapids: Baker Academic, 2015.

Fahs, B. “Compulsory bisexuality? The challenges of modern sexual fluidity.” *Journal of Bisexuality* 9 (2009): 431–449.

Felker Jones, Beth. *Practicing Christian Doctrine*. Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Academic, 2014.

Foucault, M. *The History of Sexuality*. New York: Vintage Books. Ford, 1989.

Freud, S. *Three essays on the theory of sexuality*. Translated by James Strachey. New York: Basic Books, 1951/orig. 1905.

Gaga, Lady. *Born This Way*. Santa Monica, CA: Streamline/Interscope/KonLive, 2011.

Gilad, Elon. “Judaism and Homosexuality: A Brief History,” *Haaretz* (June 2, 2016). Accessed August 8, 2022. <https://www.haaretz.com/jewish/2016-06-02/ty-article-magazine/.premium/judaism-and-homosexuality-a-brief-history/0000017f-e6a5-dc7e-adff-f6adec1f0000>

Goh, Joel. *Jesus Was Gay: Essays on Christianity and Homosexuality*. Singapore: Joel Goh, 2022. IBSB: 9798419234499, 17.

Goss, Robert E. *Queering Jesus: Beyond Jesus Acted Up*. Eugene: Resource Publications, 2002.

Grenz, Stanley J. "Jesus as the imago Dei: Image-of-God Christology and the Non-Linear Linearity of Theology." *Journal of the Evangelical Theological Society*, 47, no.4 (December, 2004): 620.

Grudem, Wayne. *Systematic Theology: An Introduction to Biblical Doctrine*. Grand Rapids MI: Zondervan, 1994.

Haynes, Jeff. *Religion in Global Politics*. London: Routledge, 2014.

Hays, Richard. "The Story of God's Son" The Identity of Jesus in the Letters of Paul." In *Seeking the Identity of Jesus: A Pilgrimage*. Edited by Beverly Roberts Gaventa and Richard B. Hays. Grand Rapids: Eerdsman, 2008.

Helminiak, Daniel A. *What the Bible Really Says About Homosexuality*. New Mexico: Alamo Square Press, 2018.

Hyena, Hank. "Was Jesus Gay: A search for the messiah's true sexuality leads to a snare of lusty theories." Accessed August 12, 2022. https://web.archive.org/web/20110217080422/http://www.salon.com/feature/1998/04/cov_10feature.html and <https://www.ci>

ty-data.com/forum/religion-spirituality/1030630-new-covenant-homosexuality-65.html

Irenaeus, “Against Heresies.” In *Volume One of Ante-Nicene Fathers* (1885–87: 11 vols). Edited by Alexander Roberts and James Donaldson. Peabody, MA: Hendrickson, 1999: 5.2.3 in 1:528.

Irizarry, Larissa A. “Queer Intimacy: Vocality in Jesus Jesus Superstar.” *Women and Music: A Journal of Gender and Culture* 24, no. 1 (2020): 162–177.

Isgro, K. L. “Troubling the Canon: Bisexuality and Queer Theory.” *Journal Of Homosexuality* 52, no. 1–2 (2006): 159–184.

Jargose, A. *Queer Theory: An Introduction*. Dunedin: Otago University Press, 1997: 3.

Jennings, T. W. *The Man Jesus Loved: Homoerotic Narratives from the New Testament*. Cleveland: Pilgrim Press, 2003.

Johnston, George. “Review of Book: The Emergence of the Catholic Tradition (100–600): Volume 1 of The Christian Tradition: A History of the Development of Doctrine.” *Religion/Sciences Religieuses* 2, no. 3 (1976): 263–264.

Karkkainen, Veli-Matti. *Christology: A Global Introduction*. Grand Rapids MI: Baker Publishing, 2016.

Kinsey, A. C., W. B. Pomeroy, C. E. Martin. *Sexual Behavior in the Human Male*. Philadelphia: W.B. Saunders, 1948.

Klein, F., B. Sepekoff, T. J. Wolf. "Sexual orientation: A multi-variable dynamic process." *Journal of Homosexuality* 11 (1985): 35–49.

Ladame, Francois. *Adolescence and Psychoanalysis: The Story and the History*. Oxfordshire: Taylor and Francis, 2018.

"LGBTIQ Ultimate Dictionary," Kids Helpline, accessed October 15, 2022. <https://kidshelpline.com.au/teens/issues/lgbtiq-ultimate-dictionary>

Martin, D. B. *Sex and the Single Saviour: Gender and Sexuality in Biblical Interpretation*. Louisville KY: Westminster John Knox, 2006.

McLaughlin, Elizabeth. "Engendering the Imago Dei: How Jesus Grounds Our Lives as Parables of the Divine Image." *Priscilla Papers: The Academic Journal of CBE International* (April 30, 2009). Accessed August 12, 2022. <https://www.cbeinternational.org/resource/article/priscilla-papers-academic-journal/engendering-imago-dei-how-Jesus-grounds-our>

Medical News Today. "What are some different types of gender identity." *Medical News Today* (n.d.), last modified August 12,

2022, <https://www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/types-of-sexuality#definition>

Michaelson, Jay. "Queer Theology and Social Transformation Twenty Years after Jesus ACTED UP." *Theology & Sexuality* 21, no. 3 (2015): 193.

Moltmann, Jurgen. *The Spirit of Life: A Universal Affirmation*, Translated by Margaret Kohl. Minneapolis: Fortress, 1992).

Moltmann, Jurgen. *The Way of Jesus Christ: Christology in Messianic Dimensions*. Translated by Margaret Kohl. Minneapolis: Fortress, 1993.

Money, J. *Gay, Straight, and In-Between: The Sexology of Erotic Orientation*. New York: Oxford University Press, 1988.

Muscarella, F. "The Evolution of Homoerotic Behavior in Humans." *Journal of Homosexuality* 40, no.1 (2000): 51–77.

Myles, Robert J. "Dandy Discipleship: A Queering of Mark's Male Disciples." *Journal of Men, Masculinities and Spirituality* 4, no. 2 (June 2010).

O'Collins, SJ, Gerald. *Christology: A Biblical, Historical, and Systematic Study of Jesus*, 2nd ed. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

Oxford English Dictionary. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2014.

Paipais, Vassilios. “Reinhold Niebuhr and the Christian realist pendulum.” *Journal of International Political Theory* 17, no. 2 (2021): 185.

Palm, Selina. “Religion and Democracy Studies in Public Theology.” Edited by Torsten Meireis and Rolf Schneider. *International Journal of Public Theology* 13, no. 1 (2019): 109.

Pannenberg, Wolfhart. *Systematic Theology*. Translated by Geoffrey W. Bromiley. Grand Rapids MI: Eerdmans, 1994.

Pedersen, W. and H. W. Kristiansen. “Homosexual Experience, Desire and Identity Among Young Adults.” *Journal of Homosexuality* 54, no.1–2 (2008): 68–102.

Poiani, A. *Animal Homosexuality: A Biosocial Approach*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2010.

Pryor, Jonathan T., González, Ángel de Jesús, and Lamb, Candace. “Exploring 20 Years of LGBTQ+ Practitioner Scholarship: Applying Scholarship to Practice?” *Journal of Student Affairs Research and Practice* (2022): 1.

Rahman, Q. “The Neurodevelopment of Sexual Orientation.” *Neuroscience and Biobehavioral Reviews* 29, no. 7 (2005): 1057–1066.

Russell, Letty M. *Church in the Round: Feminist Interpretation of the Church*. Louisville: Westminster John Knox, 1993.

Schleiermacher, Friedrich. *The Christian Faith* (2nd ed). Edited by H. R. Mackintosh and J. S. Stewart. London, T&T Clark, 1999.

Sheen, Fulton J. *The Life of Jesus*. San Francisco: Ignatius Press, 1958.

Shore-Goss, Robert E. “Queering Jesus: LGBTQI Dangerous Remembering and Imaginative Resistance.” *Journal for Interdisciplinary Biblical Studies*. (2021): 62.

Shore-Goss, Robert E., Goh, Joseph N. *Unlocking Orthodoxies for Inclusive Theologies*. London: Routledge, 2020.

Siegel, Daniel. *The Mindful Brain*. New York: W.W. Norton, 2007.

Silva, Tony J. “Straight Identity and Same-Sex Desire: Conservatism, Homophobia, and Straight Culture.” *Social Forces* 97, no. 3: 1067–1094.

Sing, O., Williams, K. E. G., and Neuberg, S. L. “Evolutionary Approches to Stereotyping and Prejudice.” Edited by C. G. Sibley, and F. K. Barlow, 21–46. *The Cambridge Handbook of the Psychology of Prejudice*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2017.

Skinner, Marilyn B. *Introduction to Roman Sexualities*. Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1997.

Stoller, R. J. and G. H. Herdt, "Theories of Origins of Male Homosexuality." *Archives of General Psychiatry* 42 (1985): 399–404.

Storms, M. D. "Theories of Sexual Orientation." *Journal of Personality & Social Psychology*. 38, no. 5 (1987): 783–792.

Triana, Ani, et al., "Influence of Adolescents Masturbation Behavior." *Enfermería Clínica* 30 (2020): 340–342.

Van Wyk, Paul, and Chrisann S. Geist. "Psychosocial Development of Heterosexual, Bisexual, and Homosexual Behavior." *Archive of Sexual Behavior* 13, no. 6 (1984): pp. 505–544.

Vines, Matthew. *God and the Gay Christian: The Biblical Case in Support of Same-Sex Relationships*. New York: Convergent Books, 2015.

Wallin, David J. *Attachment in Psychotherapy*. New York: Guilford Press, 2007.

Weinrich, J. D. "Is Homosexuality Biologically Natural?" In *Homosexuality: Social, Psychological, and Biological Issues*, edited by W. Paul and J.D. Weinrich. Beverly Hills: Sage Publications, 1987: 197–208.

Williams, Craig A. *Roman Homosexuality*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1999).

Wilson, Daniel. "A Comparison of Irenaeus' and Athanasius' Respective Descriptions of Deification in Relation to Adolf Harnack's History of Dogma." PhD Diss., Southeastern Baptist Seminary, 2005.

Wiśniewski, Łukasz. "Religious tourism in Christian sanctuaries: the implications of mixed interests for the communication of the faith." *Church, Communication and Culture* 3, no. 3 (2018): 199.

Witherington, B. *The Gospel of Mark: A Socio-Rhetorical Commentary*. Grand Rapids MI: W. B. Eerdmans, 2001: 381.

Wu, Katherine. "Love, Actually: The science behind lust, attraction, and companionship," *Harvard University: The Graduate School of Arts and Science (February 14, 2017)*. Accessed August 8, 2022. <https://sitn.hms.harvard.edu/flash/2017/love-actually-science-behind-lust-attraction-companionship/>

Zemani, Adam and Jan Coebherg. "The Nature of Consciousness." in *Clinical Neurology, Vol. 118 (3rd series) Ethical and Legal Issues in Neurology*, eds. J.L. Bernat and R. Beresford. Exeter: Department of Neurology, Peninsula Medical School, 2013: 373–407.